

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OGBUEHI****FIRST NAME: VICTORIA****PROGRAM CODE: DCTD****COURSE COD : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

WRITING A BRILLIANT RESPONSE PAPER

1) INTRODUCTION

The essence of the task undertaken in period one of the ACA-401 course, is to get students to understand the basics of writing an exceptional academic report. In the period under review, three materials were reviewed as guides to understanding what an academic Response Paper (RP) demands. The materials include a video tutorial by Laurent Cleenewerck while the other two were handouts on how to write response papers and the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack for period one respectively. This RP, consequently, is presented in four distinct parts which are – the introduction; key takeaways; writer’s opinion; and conclusions. All these are designed for instructing a fresher on how to write professionally as an academia.

Writing an RP is quite as technical as other academic writings as it has to conform to certain rubrics and styles. In writing a RP, students are expected to display a sense of expertise by making out time to read through the assigned materials; make notes where necessary; be sure they comprehend the topic under consideration; and then start off with a draft version that is eventual updated into a final document as soon as the work is done. But a student will end up making a nonsense of his work when he/she ignorantly or deliberately refuses to cite the source of his information – an action which is called ‘plagiarism’ and considered an offence. An RP though not a typical academic report owing to the required length and citation options must be properly structured and persuasive enough to gain the approval of academic pundits.

2) **KEY TAKEAWAYS**

Here, let us consider some of the prominent takeaways from the reference materials -

a) The American or the British English

Laurent talked about choosing language options in writing and emphasized the need to stay consistent regardless of whether a writer wishes to use the American or the British English (Cleenewerck n.d.). Both the American and the British English are different variants of English language that are ‘more similar than different’ (EUCLID 2019, 27). Understanding the fact that whatever style of English that a writer has opted for would impact the footing noting style and quotes is imperative. A writer that has opted for the American English will have to conform to using the ‘full stop’ before the closing quote but in the British pattern; full stop comes after the closing quote (Cleenewerck n.d.). That is interesting, right?

b) Short and Long Quotes

Laurent pointed out the difference between citing a short and a long quote. One of the leanings here is that any quote that is more than four lines should be indented and not enclosed in quotation marks (Cleenewerck n.d.). ‘Something that is difficult for students to understand is styling... a rule of styles is how to make citations and references’ (Cleenewerck, n.d.). Paraphrasing is advisable because it shows that a student has comprehended fully what he/she has read and could explain that in his/her own words without misrepresenting the source. That is a difficult one though as it goes beyond copying someone else’s work and then alternating some words or perhaps, altering the sequence to obscure the actual meaning of what has been copied (EUCLID 2019, 7-8). In paraphrasing therefore, students are expected to act ethically by conveying the exact meaning of the phrases or sentences in their own words and then cite the originator. Whether quotations are indented as block quotes or enclosed in quotation marks, citing the source is a mandatory requirement (EUCLID 2019, 5-6).

c) Essay writing

Academic essays are expected to be objective and swaying. The crux is to proof to your readers that your reports are based on facts after consulting other materials that are typically cited. Unlike other forms of writing, the academic writer is expected back his/her assertions with verifiable proofs (EUCLID 2019, 1). So, if you must write a successful essay you must start early; and be willing to study as many materials as possible. Besides, if you have been assigned a specific topic you need to be sure that you understand what the subject matter is all about so you can respond appropriately.

Additionally, you will have to make notes as you read through other people’s works, so you do not forget them when you are settled to writing proper. Once this is done,

you write your first draft which will serve as an aid in the final write-up where you have to ensure that the paper is well structured with logical transition from the introduction to conclusions (EUCLID 2019, 1-3). It is important to note that every work cited in an academic writing must be cited as a matter of ethics and professionalism else, a researcher could become liable to plagiarism which constitute a serious offence in the academia. In as much as it is important to quote to buttress a point, it is also helpful to note that quotes should be used scantily if we must present our works as our original idea.

d) Do not cite!

The importance of citing all references made in the cause of a research report cannot be overemphasized however, there are instances when citations will not be required. There is no need for a citation when the information capture is of public knowledge (EUCLID 2019, 9-10). For example, the fact that Christians belief that Jesus Christ is the son of God is a general knowledge. It is a general knowledge that mosquitos bite is responsible for malaria. The fact that Donald Trump is the President of United States is also a general knowledge that do not require citation.

e) Using the Latin words in an English paper

In all formal, technical, business, and academic writing refraining from the use of Latin abbreviations is recommended so as not to get the readers confused and/or have the readers misrepresent the author. (EUCLID 2019, 56). Because a combination of Latin words and acronyms makes an academic writing ambiguous, such abbreviations are better used in footnotes and other informal writings. It is therefore desirable to write in plain English because the plain English is simple and direct (EUCLID 2019, 56) and capable of being understood by a non-subject matter expert.

3) WRITER'S PERSPECTIVE

It was quite insightful studying the reference materials and listening to the video for this period. I have always known before now that the American and the British English are two different variants of English language, but I never knew or thought that same words from both variants could be pronounced differently as was the case in one of the reference materials (EUCLID 2019, 27 -28). This has helped me answer the question as to why the two-pronunciation apps on my cell phone pronounces same 'words' differently at times depending on the 'word' that is being pronounced. For me, it takes consistent practice and commitment to perfect the act of academic writing because it requires time which is a resource that is becoming scarcer by the day. This is why plagiarism must never be treated with levity as it is unfair to steal someone else's intellectual asset that was achieved through a lot of sleepless nights and then be punished with just a 'failing grade.'

4) CONCLUSIONS

ACA-401 is quite an interesting course that lays the foundation for the principles of mastering the act of academic writing. Missing the points highlighted in this course especially in period one is tantamount to struggling throughout the duration of this program. So, the earlier we understood the nitty-gritty of writing a RP the better and easier it would be to cope in the program. If there is a time to take ownership of this program it is now in period one since the Ph.D. program is all about writing and more writings.

REFERENCES

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<https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed May 23, 2020).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

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